

As-deposited and dewetted Cu layers on plasma treated glass: Adhesion study and its effect on biological response

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ABSTRACT

Improving the adhesion of nanosized copper films to a glass substrate is vital for their application in electronics and medicine, as it enhances their overall reliability. For this purpose, we employed Ar plasma etching (240 s) and magnetron sputtering to create copper layers on a glass substrate. Furthermore, we investigated the effect of subsequent solid state dewetting (at 300 °C) of Cu nanolayers on the interface stability. Increasing the sputtering time resulted in elevated copper concentration, UV-Vis absorption, conductivity, and surface roughness. The as-deposited and dewetted samples exhibited very good wettability with water contact angles below 60°. Importantly, plasma treatment improved the adhesion of the Cu layers to the glass. Subsequent dewetting accelerated surface diffusion and the oxidation of Cu atoms, causing structural and morphological changes. The presence of CuO after dewetting caused loss of the surface plasmon resonance (SPR) band in the UV-Vis spectrum and a decrease in sample conductivity due to the transformation of the copper layer from a metal to an oxide. Biological testing revealed a more pronounced bactericidal effect for the as-deposited Cu layer against *E. coli* and *S. epidermidis* on contrary to dewetted samples. The similar cytotoxic trend was observed for human dermal fibroblasts and hepatocytes. Nonetheless, biological testing confirmed better cell adhesion on dewetted Cu layers compared to the as-deposited ones. Therefore, our copper nanostructured samples could find application as antibacterial coatings of biomedical devices.

1. Introduction

The copper-coated glass surface has a great potential because of its broad spectrum of applications, such as solar cells [1,2], plasmonic devices [3], gas sensors [4], Raman spectroscopy [5], electrochromic coatings [6] and data storage [7]. In general, when it comes to the development of detectors and other electronic components, these materials are beneficial for their cost efficiency, stability in an oxidizing atmosphere, and sustainability [8,9]. In medicine, Cu and CuO films are extensively used for bone regeneration [10], preparation of antimicrobial and antimycotic surfaces [11–13], burn skin treatments, wound-healing [14,15] and angiogenic promotion *in vitro* and *in vivo* [16]. However, Cu NPs have shown serious cytotoxicity against the kidney, liver, and spleen of mice after oral application. The value of LD₅₀

value after Cu NP (23. nm) ingestion in mice has been reported to be 413 mg kg⁻¹ [12,17]. Therefore, nanosized Cu structures on solid substrates deserve further investigation.

Metal oxide films, including Cu oxide films, could be prepared by various deposition techniques such as chemical vapor deposition, sol-gel procedures, thermal evaporation, electrodeposition, spray pyrolysis, pulsed laser deposition, and plasma-based ion implantation and deposition. The deposition technique and its conditions alter the physical and chemical properties of the layer [2,18,19]. In the case of cathode sputtering, the properties of CuO thin films are affected by (i) sputtering pressure [20], (ii) power [21], (iii) temperature of the substrate [22], (iv) working gas flow [23], and (v) electrode distance [24,25].

One of the most influential parameters connected with nanosized structures is the localized surface plasmon resonance (LSPR). LSPR

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Table 1

XPS results of element concentration Si, O, Cu and C (at. %) on surface of pristine glass, as-deposited (RT) and dewetted (300 °C) Cu layers on plasma treated glass sputtered with copper for 10 and 400 s.

Sample	Concentration of elements (at. %)			
	Si(2s)	O(1s)	Cu(2p _{3/2})	C(1s)
glass	20.4	55.0	-	24.6
glass_pl	14.9	51.0	-	34.1
glass_pl_Cu_10s_RT	8.8	42.9	13.7	34.6
glass_pl_Cu_10s_300 °C	12.5	49.5	7.3	30.7
glass_pl_Cu_400s_RT	-	25.2	11.7	63.1
glass_pl_Cu_400s_300 °C	-	38.6	27.3	34.1

comes from the collective oscillation of the conduction electrons due to interactions between the incident light and the conduction band electrons of the metal. It leads to an increase in the strong electric field around the nanostructures by pushing the electromagnetic energy into the nanosized region [26]. The LSPR sensitivity of metal nanostructures prepared on a dielectric substrate strongly depends on their size, spacing, and shape. The morphological and electrical properties of the underlying substrate also affect LSPR in nanostructures [27–30].

Thin metal layers deposited on substrates have a high surface energy because of their high surface to volume ratio. Thus, solid-state dewetting (SSD) of thin metal layers results in the formation of isolated islands. Owing to SSD, a thin metal layer decreases the surface to volume ratio, minimizing the free energy of the system. SSD occurs when an external disorder is introduced at the interface between the layer and the

Fig. 1. (A) Deconvolution of the Cu2p region of as-deposited (RT) and dewetted (300 °C) Cu layers on plasma treated glass sputtered with copper for 400 s (s means the satellite shake up peak of CuO). (B) The deconvoluted spectra of Cu2p_{3/2} of as-deposited (RT) and annealed (300 °C) Cu layers on plasma treated glass sputtered with copper for 400 s

Fig. 2. (A) UV-Vis absorption spectra of Cu layers sputtered with copper for 5–600 s of as-deposited (RT) and dewetted (300 °C) layers. (B) Plots of $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ versus photon energy ($h\nu$) of the as-deposited (RT) and dewetted (300 °C) Cu layers on plasma treated glass sputtered with copper for 400 s.

substrate for example by isothermal annealing, pulse laser heating and cold plasma treatment [31]. The SSD process consists of the hole formation followed by their growth until the thin layer is transformed into an island-like structure. Nucleation can be either homogeneous or heterogeneous depending on the primary microstructure, such as crystallographic structure, defects, grain size, foreign inclusions, residual stresses, and the morphology of the as-deposited thin layers [32,33].

Adhesion between thin metal layer and rigid substrate often represents limitations in its technological and biomedical applications [34]. Adhesion at the interface is an important parameter for determining the stability and overall reliability of the system. Another way to increase interface stability is to modify layer properties. The adhesion of thin metal films is affected by various factors, such as residual stress,

interfacial reactions, film thickness and film microstructure, which are difficult to separate from each other. Therefore, it is crucial to find out how the properties of thin metal layer may change its adhesion [35,36].

This research underscores the importance of adhesion enhancement in tailoring the properties of nanosized copper films for diverse electronic and medical applications. The improvement in adhesion of the metal/glass interface in this work was performed by plasma treatment. This study investigates surface properties of as-deposited and dewetted Cu layers such as chemical composition, charge, wettability and morphology as crucial parameters for biological performance. Present study builds on our previous paper in which Cu layers were sputtered on just ethanol cleaned glass substrates [37]. Mechanical properties (adhesion) were studied by nanoindentation. Antibacterial tests were

Fig. 3. Sheet electrical resistance (Ω) of as-deposited (RT) and dewetted (300 °C) Cu layers on plasma treated glass sputtered with copper for 5–600 s.

Fig. 4. SEM micrographs displaying the surface morphology of as-deposited (RT) and dewetted (300 °C) Cu layers on plasma treated glass sputtered with copper for 400 s.

performed according to the standard protocol against *E. coli* and *S. epidermidis*. Cytotoxicity tests were performed on normal human dermal fibroblasts (NHDF) and hepatocytes (HepG2) since CuNPs can have negative effect on human health and can accumulate in the liver.

2. Experimental part

2.1. Materials and sample preparation

Thin Cu layers were deposited on plasma treated glass (borosilicate coverslips, thickness 0.13–0.16 mm, size $18 \times 18 \text{ mm}^2$, Menzel Gläser GmbH, DE) by magnetron sputtering. Firstly, the pristine glass (labelled as glass) was cleaned in ethanol (EtOH, 96 %, Penta s.r.o, CZ) and dried in a stream of nitrogen (N_2 , purity 99.999 %, Siad s.r.o., CZ). Second, the pristine glass was treated with DC argon plasma discharge using the BAL-TEC SCD 050 device (BAL-TEC AG, CH) for 240 s with a discharge power of 8.3 W and at a pressure of 10 Pa. The purity of working gas was 99.999 % (Ar^+ , Siad s.r.o., CZ). Then, Cu layers were deposited on the glass substrates at a distance of 14 cm using Quorum Q300T ES coater (Quorum Technologies Inc., UK). Magnetron sputtering was carried out at laboratory temperature using the Cu target ($\rho = 8.96 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$, purity of 99.99 %, Goodfellow Ltd., UK) as a metal source and Ar pressure of 1 Pa (purity of 99.999 %, Siad s.r.o., CZ). The sputtering time was in a range of 5–600 s at the sputtering current of 60 mA (referred to as as-deposited or glass_pl_Cu_RT). Subsequent SSD was performed in Binder FD 23 oven (Binder GmbH, DE) under atmospheric pressure at 300 °C for 1 h (labelled as dewetted or glass_pl_Cu_300 °C). The samples were stored under laboratory conditions.

2.2. Analytical methods

The chemical composition of pristine glass, plasma treated glass, as-deposited and dewetted Cu layers on glass was determined by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) using an ESCAProbe P Spectrometer (Omicron Nanotechnology GmbH, DE). The take-off angle of the emitted electrons was 0° to the surface normal (i.e. perpendicular). The analyzed area was 1 mm^2 . The X-ray source was monochromatic Al $K\alpha$ radiation ($h\nu = 1486.7 \text{ eV}$) with a step size of 0.05 eV. XPS analysis was performed at a pressure of $2 \times 10^{-8} \text{ Pa}$. Calibration of the spectrometer was accomplished by periodic measurement of Cu, Ag and Au. The charge neutraliser was applied during analysis. The samples were not sputter etched prior to analysis. Charge referencing was performed by setting the Si 2p line from the glass substrate at 103.0 eV [38]. Shirley background was used in the analysis of element concentrations.

Ultraviolet-visible (UV-Vis) spectroscopy was used to characterise the optical behaviour of the as-deposited and dewetted Cu layers on plasma treated glass. Absorption spectra were evaluated using a Lambda 25 spectrophotometer (PerkinElmer Inc., US) in the spectral range of 400–800 nm, scan speed $240 \text{ nm}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ and step of 1 nm. The reference spectrum of pristine glass was subtracted from the collected spectrum of glass with Cu layers. The optical absorption error values were lower than 1.5 %.

The sheet resistance (R_s) of the as-deposited and dewetted Cu layers on plasma treated glass was determined using the KEITHLEY 487 picoammeter by the Ohm's method. To reduce the effect of atmospheric humidity, electrical measurements were performed at a pressure of 8 Pa. The measurement error was less than $\pm 10 \%$.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM, Lyra dual beam microscope, Tescan a. s., CZ) was applied for evaluation of surface morphology of pristine glass, plasma treated glass, as-deposited and dewetted Cu layers on plasma treated glass at micrometer level. SEM analysis was performed in the secondary electron (SE) imaging mode with accelerating voltage of 5 kV. The magnification of the presented SEM images is $50,000 \times$ with $4 \times 4 \mu\text{m}^2$ scan size. To prevent surface charging, samples were attached to the holder with carbon conductive tape and coated with 20 nm thick Au layer (purity of Au target 99.99 %, Safina a.s., CZ). The Au layer was prepared using sputtering device Q300T (Quorum Technologies Inc., UK). Cu concentration (in at. %) was evaluated by energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS, X-MaxN analyser, 80 mm² SDD detector, Oxford Instruments Plc., UK).

The mechanical characterisation of Cu layers on glass was tested

Fig. 5. The scratch test images characterizing the mechanical properties of pristine glass, plasma treated glass, as-deposited (RT) and dewetted (300 °C) Cu layers on plasma treated glass sputtered with copper for 400 s.

Table 2

Results of scratch test performed on Cu layers sputtered on plasma treated glass substrate.

Critical loads for the beginning of layer failure (mN)			
glass_Cu_RT	glass_Cu_300 °C	glass_pl_Cu_RT	glass_pl_Cu_300 °C
0.93 ± 0.10	0.38 ± 0.04	2.91 ± 0.51	0.48 ± 0.05

Fig. 6. The images of scotch tape test characterizing adhesion of as-deposited (RT) and dewetted (300 °C) Cu layers on plasma treated glass sputtered with copper for 400 s. Red circles highlight the exposed area.

using Nano Scratch Tester (Anton Paar GmbH, AT) with a diamond sphero-conical indenter with a tip radius of 1 µm. Three scratches were prepared on surfaces of pristine glass, plasma treated glass, as-deposited (RT) and dewetted (300 °C) Cu layers on plasma treated glass sputtered with Cu for 400 s. The test consisted of applying the load gradually increasing from 0.05 to 10 mN at a length of 300 µm. The critical loads (L_c) indicating the onset of damage (critical loads for the beginning of

layer failure) were determined by optical analysis. Adhesion of as-deposited and dewetted Cu layers on plasma treated glass sputtered with Cu for 400 s was verified also by scotch tape test.

Atomic force microscope Dimension ICON (AFM, Bruker Corp., US) was employed to investigate the surface morphology and roughness of the prepared samples at nanometer level. AFM analysis was performed with ScanAsyst mode in the air using a silicon tip on a nitride cantilever with a spring constant of 0.4 N·m⁻¹. The acquired data were processed by NanoScope Analysis software to obtain the average surface roughness values (R_a). The size of the scans was 300 × 300 nm². The thickness of the as-deposited and dewetted Cu layers was determined by AFM using a scratch test.

The static water contact angle (WCA) of the samples was determined using a DSA 100 goniometer (KRÜSS GmbH, DE). WCA analysis was performed at laboratory temperature at fifteen points on five samples. The volume of drops of distilled water was (2.0 ± 0.2) µl. The WCA were examined using the ADVANCE software.

The zeta potential was evaluated using a SurPASS electrokinetic analyser (Anton Paar, GmbH, AT) in a cell with an adjustable gap (of about 100 µm). Samples were measured at laboratory temperature in an electrolytic solution of KCl with a concentration of 0.001 mol·L⁻¹ at a pH in the range of 6.1-6.2. The streaming current method and the Helmholtz-Smoluchowski equation were used to determine the zeta potential with an experimental error of 5 %.

2.3. Biological tests

2.3.1. Antibacterial effect

The antibacterial effect of the as-deposited and dewetted Cu layers on plasma treated glass was measured using the drop plate method. The measurement was carried out using two bacterial strains: the gram-positive bacteria (G+) *Staphylococcus epidermis* (*S. epidermis*; DBM 2124) and the gram-negative bacteria (G-) *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*; DBM 3138). One colony was used to prepare the inoculum, which was transferred sterily with a bacteriological loop in 4 ml (*S. epidermidis*) and 25 ml (*E. coli*) of Luria-Bertani (LB) liquid medium. Subsequently, the inocula were incubated overnight on an orbital shaker at 37 °C. Next,

Fig. 7. AFM images displaying the surface morphology and roughness (R_a , in nm) of pristine glass, as-deposited (RT) and dewetted (300 °C) Cu layers on plasma treated glass sputtered with copper for 10 and 400 s.

they were diluted in sterile phosphate buffered saline (PBS) to final concentration of approx. $3 \cdot 10^3$ (*S. epidermidis*) and $2 \cdot 10^3$ (*E. coli*) per mL. The samples in triplicates were immersed in 2 mL of the bacterial suspension in tubes for 2 h at room temperature. Then, five drops (25 μ L) from each testing tube were placed on plate count agar (PCA, Oxoid, containing tryptone 5 g L⁻¹, yeast extract 2.5 g L⁻¹, glucose 1 g L⁻¹, agar 15 g L⁻¹) culture dish. Cultivation was carried out overnight. The next day, the number of colony-forming units (CFU) was calculated. All experiments were performed under sterile conditions.

All antibacterial tests were carried out in three independent measurements, each of them including five repetitions (i.e., five drops for CFU counting). To show the differences between the samples and pristine glass, the two-sample t-test assuming equal variance (Excel, Microsoft Office, US) was done.

2.3.2. In vitro cellular tests

The primary normal human dermal fibroblasts (NHDF, Lonza Group AG, CH) and the hepatocyte carcinoma cell line (HepG2) were used to determine the cytotoxicity of as-deposited and dewetted Cu layers on plasma treated glass.

Firstly, the eluates were made from the prepared layers. The as-

deposited and dewetted Cu layers on plasma treated glass as well as a glass and TC-plastic well (CTRL) were incubated with a cell cultivation medium (DMEM – Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Medium, Gibco, UK; with the addition of 10 % heat-inactivated fetal bovine serum (FBS, PAA Laboratories GmbH, AT), penicillin (20 μ L ml⁻¹, Sigma-Aldrich Corp., US) and streptomycin (20 μ L ml⁻¹, Sigma-Aldrich Corp., US)) for 24 h. Then these eluates were poured onto the cells (pre-seeded for 24 h - HepG2 1.5×10^4 cell cm⁻²; NHDF 1.0×10^4 cell cm⁻²) and incubated for 24 h.

Secondly, these Cu layers were inserted into 48-well plates and the cells were seeded directly on them at the density and the medium mentioned above and cultivated at 37 °C and in an atmosphere of 5 % CO₂ in an incubator for 24 h.

Phase contrast images of the cells were taken by IX71 microscope (Olympus Corp., JP) with CPlan FI 10x objective just before any further analysis or staining.

The effect of different treatments was determined using analysis of cell metabolic activity (Cell Titer 96 Aqueous One Solution Cell proliferation Assay, MTS, Promega Corp., US) performed according to the standard protocol. This test shows not only the cell metabolic activity but also the cell number, thus it is generally used as a test for

Fig. 8. Photographs of distilled water drops on pristine glass, as-deposited (RT) and dewetted (300 °C) Cu layers on plasma treated glass sputtered with copper for 10 and 400 s.

Fig. 9. Zeta potential of pristine glass, plasma treated glass, as-deposited (RT) and dewetted (300 °C) Cu layers on plasma treated glass sputtered with copper for 10 and 400 s.

cytotoxicity. Absorbance was measured using multi-detection multi-plate reader (The Spark, Tecan Group Ltd., CH) at 490 nm and reference at 655 nm. All measured results were normalised (in percentage) with respect to cells cultivated on the control glass (set as 100 %) and compared with standard cell cultivation on TC-plastic (CTRL).

After measuring the MTS absorbance, the staining solution from the

Fig. 10. Number of CPU of *E. coli* and *S. epidermidis* on glass samples from drop antibacterial test against *E. coli* and *S. epidermidis*. Samples were tested after each stage of preparation: pristine glass, plasma treated glass, as-deposited (RT) and dewetted (300 °C) Cu layers on plasma treated glass sputtered with copper for 10 and 400 s. * stands for statistically significant decrease, $p < 0.05$ of sample compared to pristine glass.

Fig. 11. Images of cultivation dishes with *E. coli* and *S. epidermidis* bacterial colonies. Images are those of control test (CTRL) and bacteria exposed to pristine glass, plasma treated glass (240 s), as-deposited (RT) and dewetted (300 °C) Cu layers on plasma treated glass sputtered with copper for 10 and 400 s.

cells cultivated with eluates was discarded and a solution for fluorescent staining of DNA was added (CyQUANT NF Cell Proliferation Assay Kit, Invitrogen). The cells were incubated at 37 °C and in an atmosphere of 5 % CO₂ in an incubator for 1 h. Fluorescence was measured using multi-detection multi-plate reader (The Spark, Tecan Group Ltd., CH) at excitation of 485 nm and emission of 530 nm. All measured results were normalised (in percentage) with respect to cells cultivated on the control glass (set as 100 %) and compared with standard cell cultivation on TC-plastic (CTRL).

Metabolic activity of single cell was determined by calculation of the ratio of absorbance value from MTS test and fluorescence value of CyQUANT assay. All measured results were normalised (in percentage) with respect to cells cultivated on the control glass (set as 100 %) and compared with standard cell cultivation on TC-plastic (CTRL).

The cells cultivated directly on the samples were rinsed with PBS and marked with the Live/Dead Assay in a CO₂ incubator at 37 °C for 30 min. After incubation, the samples were rinsed, and images were taken in the green channel (excitation 470–495 nm, emission 450–550 nm) visualizing calcein-detectable cellular esterase activity of live cells and in the red channel (excitation 510–550 nm, emission 570 nm) visualizing the nuclei of dead cells in which Ethidium homodimer (EthD) is intercalated into cellular DNA of damaged cells. Olympus IX71 fluorescence microscope (Olympus Corp., JP) with a DP74 colour camera was used.

Statistical analysis was performed using STATISTICA (StatSoft s.r.o., CZ) software from three independent experiments performed in duplicates. The nonparametric Wilcoxon matched pairs test was used to determine significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between the datasets of the untreated control and the rest of the variables.

3. Results and discussion

Surface properties of material that have been implied in cell adhesion are surface charge and energy, hydrophilicity and surface roughness. For example, surface with negative charge generally exhibits less bacterial adhesion because of electric double layer repulsion, since most bacterial cell surfaces carry a negative charge. On the other hand, materials with positive surface charge inhibits bacterial growth since they can captivate and damage the bacterial cell walls and kill the bacteria. The increase in the surface free energy and the decrease in the contact angle leads to a reduced bacterial adhesion. A highly wettable surface leads to a reduced bacterial adhesion. Further, flat surfaces show lower bacterial adhesion than rough ones. Another very important parameter for biomedical applications is the adhesion of metal layers to underlying substrate [38]. Therefore, we have focused on investigation of the above-mentioned parameters.

The elemental composition (Si, O, Cu, C) of as-deposited and dewetted Cu layers as examined by XPS is summarized in Table 1. Every sample contains adventitious carbon at different atomic concentrations. The varying amount of carbon depends on the surface chemistry of each

Fig. 12. Light microscopy images of fibroblasts (NHDF) and liver cells (HepG2) treated with 24 h-eluates from the different Cu layers for 24 h (just before any analysis). Scale bar is 100 µm.

Fig. 13. Number of fibroblasts (NHDF) and liver cells (HepG2) (A) and their metabolic activity of single cell (B) treated with 24 h-eluates from the different layers for 24 h. ** statistically significant difference ($p = 0.05$) to values on glass (100 %), \$\$ statistically significant difference ($p = 0.05$) between cells in eluates from different Cu layers.

Fig. 14. Light microscopy images of NHDF and HepG2 cultivated on the different Cu layers for 24 h (just before any analysis). Scale bar is 100 μm .

sample, which affects the subsequent adsorption of aliphatic hydrocarbons from the atmosphere. Greczynski et al. reported that adventitious carbon contamination increases with exposure time to the ambient atmosphere and changes with laboratory conditions and seasons of the year. These contaminants cannot be removed without affecting the underlying film [39]. Pristine and plasma treated glass contains nearly the same amount of Si and O on the very surface. Nevertheless, plasma-modified glass contains more carbon due to the creation of active sites during plasma treatment, and thus easier adsorbs hydrocarbons from the atmosphere [40]. The concentration of Si and O is decreased as a result of plasma etching. [41]. After 10 s of Cu sputtering, a discontinuous layer is created and the chemical composition is also affected by the underlying substrate. Subsequent SSD causes oxidation (oxygen content 49.5 at. %) and structural rearrangement of the Cu layer. Copper is transformed into islands, hence its concentration decreases (7.3 at. %) and the glass substrate predominates (Si 12.5 at. %). After 400 s of Cu sputtering, a continuous layer is created and no Si is detected. Oxidation and redistribution of Cu layer is more pronounced. The concentration of oxygen increased from 25.2 to 38.6 at. % and Cu from 11.7 to 27.3 at. %. Deconvolution of the Cu2p region together with

details of the Cu2p_{3/2} peak of as-deposited and dewetted Cu layers sputtered with copper for 400 s is depicted in Fig. 1 A, B. The XPS spectra of as-deposited and dewetted Cu2p showed characteristic doublet peaks of SOS (spin orbit splitting) and the shakeup satellite peaks (labelled as s) were observed at about 12 and 8 eV of binding energies higher than that of the Cu2p peak (Fig. 1A). The presence of satellite peaks s revealed formation of CuO [19]. For the as-deposited sample (Fig. 1B, on the left), the Cu 2p_{3/2} peaks were curve fitted with three species corresponding to bulk/Cu₂O (931.8 eV, FWHM 1.19 eV, 69.1 at. %), CuO (934.1 eV, FWHM 2.0 eV, 19.4 at. %) and two CuO satellite peaks (942.5 eV, FWHM 1.6 eV, 6.4 at. % and 944.3 eV, FWHM 1.6 eV, 5.0 at. %). Similarly, deconvolution of Cu2p_{3/2} of the dewetted sample (Fig. 1B, on the right) showed three components corresponding to bulk/Cu₂O (933.1 eV, FWHM 1.99 eV, 26.4 at. %), CuO (934.3 eV, FWHM 2.94 eV, 38.4 at. %) and two CuO satellite peaks (941.2 eV, FWHM 2.74 eV, 24.3 at. % and 943.7 eV, FWHM 1.62 eV, 10.9 at. %). From these results, it could be concluded that the as-deposited samples consist of bulk copper or Cu₂O with a small portion of CuO. While for the dewetted sample CuO prevails [42].

UV-Vis spectra were measured to monitor optical changes of as-

Fig. 15. Metabolic activity (cytotoxicity) of NHDF and HepG2 cells on as-deposited (RT) and dewetted (300 °C) Cu layers on plasma treated glass sputtered with copper (for 400 s) after 24 h cultivation. ** statistically significant difference ($p = 0.05$) to values on glass (100 %), \$\$ statistically significant difference ($p = 0.05$) between cells on Cu layers.

deposited and dewetted Cu layers on plasma treated glass (see Fig. 2A). On the left side of Fig. 2A the absorption spectra of as-deposited Cu layers are depicted. These spectra show typical absorption spectra of bulk metals with absorption increasing with sputtering time. The LSPR band

exhibits a red shift from 622 to 644 nm, which is in good accordance with published literature [19,43]. On the other hand, dewetted samples showed no LSPR band suggesting oxidation of Cu (see Fig. 2A, on the right). This is in good agreement with the XPS results. CuO is known to be a transition metal oxide with a monoclinic lattice structure, a varying energy band gap (1.2–4.0 eV) and a *p-type* semiconductor [2,44]. To obtain the optical band gap value of the Cu thin layers, we have applied the Tauc's equation [45] to make plots of $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ vs. $h\nu$, and extrapolate their linear parts to the energy axis [9,46]. For samples glass_pl_Cu_400s_RT and glass_pl_400s_300°C we have received values of the optical band gap of 1.95 and 2.2 eV, respectively (see Fig. 2B). Obtained values of optical band gaps correspond to semiconducting CuO (1.95 eV) and Cu₂O (2.2 eV), which is in good agreement with the literature [19].

Fig. 3 shows the sheet resistance of nanostructured Cu layers. As the sputtering time increases, the structure transforms from an electrically discontinuous to an electrically continuous layer [47]. This phenomenon is associated with a sudden drop in sheet resistance called the percolation threshold [48]. For as-deposited samples, the electrically continuous layer is formed after 100 s of Cu sputtering (see Fig. 3). Thus, the layers with a sputtering time below 100 s could be considered discontinuous, while the layers with a sputtering time above 100 s are electrically continuous. The sheet resistance decreases from $2.1 \cdot 10^{14}$ down to 35 Ω , i.e. 13 orders of magnitude. On the other hand, dewetted sample showed a steady decrease in sheet resistance with sputtering time, i.e. a drop from $5.8 \cdot 10^{13}$ to $3.1 \cdot 10^7 \Omega$. In this case, the milder decrease of sheet resistance is connected to the presence of the semi-conducting CuO [8].

SEM micrographs of pristine, plasma treated and Cu sputtered glass are shown in Fig. 4. Pristine and plasma treated glass have flat surfaces and are captured for comparison with nanostructured samples. Only samples sputtered with Cu for 400 s are presented in this figure because samples with 10 s of sputtering time could not be captured sharply due to their very fine structure, which is beyond the resolution of SEM analysis. Compared to our previous study, the as-deposited Cu layers on plasma treated glass exhibit a smooth texture [37]. On the other hand, the dewetted sample has a rugged morphology consisting of isolated island-like nanostructures of CuO [49]. CuO grains seem to have the same size and homogeneous distribution on the sample surface. Increase in Cu concentration from 3.9 to 5.0 at. % after the dewetting process confirmed redistribution of the as-deposited layer (see above). The discrepancy in the results of the XPS and EDS analyses is caused by the

Fig. 16. Fluorescence microscopy images of live (green Calcein dye) and dead (red Ethidium dye) NHDF and HepG2 cells cultivated on the different Cu layers for 24 h stained with Live/Dead Assay.

different depths from which the information is obtained.

After mechanical evaluation of the layers in the form of scratch tests, the morphologies of the scratches differed qualitatively. The more pronounced failure of the Cu layer occurred after annealing (Fig. 5), which corresponded to lower critical forces at the beginning of the layer failure (see Table 2). Plasma modification of the glass substrate improved adhesion of Cu layers to glass substrate. After both sputtering and subsequent annealing, the adhesion of the layers to the substrate was better in the case of the plasma-modified substrate than in the unmodified ones (see Table 2 and our previous study Ref. [37]). Adhesion of the as-deposited and dewetted Cu layers on the plasma treated glass sputtered with Cu for 400 s was also certified by scotch tape test (see Fig. 6). From this figure can be seen that dewetted sample shows slightly better adhesion than as-deposited one due to visible disruption of Cu layer.

Living organisms react with the material both at the micrometer and at the nanometer levels, so it is important to know how sample morphology changes at each level. AFM images with scan size of $300 \times 300 \text{ nm}^2$ of as-deposited and dewetted layers are displayed in Fig. 7. Pristine and plasma treated glass have very flat and smooth surfaces with surface roughness (R_a) of 0.2 nm. The same result was obtained from the SEM analysis (Fig. 4). According to the XPS results, the difference between these two samples is that the plasma treated surface contains adsorbed aliphatic hydrocarbons from the atmosphere. After 10 s of sputtering (glass_pl_Cu_10s_RT), the surface morphology and roughness ($R_a = 0.2 \text{ nm}$) are similar to the plasma treated glass. After such a short sputtering time, the plasma modification has the main effect on the sample morphology. For its dewetted counterpart, there is a dramatic change in the surface morphology. The surface roughness increases 9 times ($R_a = 1.8 \text{ nm}$), and an island-like structure is clearly visible. After 400 s, the glass is fully covered with a Cu grain-like layer and surface roughness decreases ($R_a = 1.0 \text{ nm}$). Dewetting of this sample (glass_pl_Cu_400s_300 °C) creates smaller and mutually connected grains, and surface roughness increases to $R_a = 2.5 \text{ nm}$. The rearrangement of Cu atoms and their oxidation due to SSD was also confirmed by the change in layer thickness. The thickness of as-deposited and dewetted Cu layer was 24.0 and 50.3 nm, respectively. Thickness of Cu layers sputtered for 10 s was below 1 nm.

In addition to the surface morphology, cell interactions also depend on a surface wettability. For materials used in tissue engineering, it is desirable to have moderate surface roughness and hydrophilicity (i.e. contact angle lower than 90°). On such surface, cells can easily adhere, spread and proliferate [50]. Images of the contact angle of distilled water (WCA) after each modification step are shown in Fig. 8. After plasma treatment (glass_pl), a dramatic decrease of WCA down to 8° is observed. As XPS revealed, this behaviour is connected to the highest concentration of oxygen functional groups and adsorbed hydrocarbons from the ambient atmosphere. The as-deposited samples (both 10 and 400 s) have a similar WCA around 30° , which increases after the dewetting process. The dewetted sample glass_pl_Cu_400s_300 °C has the highest WCA due to the combination of the highest surface roughness together with the highest concentration of CuO. This phenomenon is described in literature as the lotus effect, the higher the surface roughness, the higher the WCA is observed [51].

For the cell adhesion, a surface charge is also very important [52]. It can be determined by electrokinetic analysis and zeta potential measurement. As is clear from Fig. 9, after plasma treatment, the zeta potential changes significantly in comparison with the pristine sample due to the presence of oxygen polar groups. Other important changes were observed after (i) Cu deposition and (ii) dewetting process. As we can see from Fig. 9, sputtering of Cu for 10 s lead to only slight changes in zeta potential in comparison with pristine glass. This is probably due to Cu structures do not cover the entire surface and create only some Cu islands on the glass, and the glass substrate plays an important role for surface charge. However, 400 s of Cu sputtering result in dramatic changes in the surface charge. Significantly positive surface charge given by the total coverage of the glass by Cu layer was obtained and it

can play a key role for cell attachment in comparison to other tested samples. The more consistent Cu coating with a higher amount of Cu on this sample can have antibacterial effect. After dewetting of glass_pl_Cu_400s sample dramatic change of value was observed. The zeta potential went back to a highly negative value, so the effect on the bacterial adhesion can be expected similarly to other tested samples.

Thus, the antibacterial properties of the prepared materials were tested against the two most common bacterial strains – a gram-positive *S. epidermidis* and a gram-negative *E. coli*. Antibacterial activity was represented by the number of colony producing units (CPU) in the bacterial suspension after sample exposure (Fig. 10). The *E. coli* bacterial strain shows a statistically significant decrease in CPU for all tested samples compared to pristine glass (labelled as glass). This shows that the used modifications cause antibacterial effects and the glass_pl_Cu_400s_RT sample showed the strongest one, almost 35 %. For *S. epidermidis* bacterial strain, the difference between glass and almost all modified samples is not statistically significant, which suggests that the modification does not affect the antibacterial properties towards this strain. The only sample that showed any significant antibacterial effect compared to pristine glass was glass_pl_Cu_400s_RT, where the decrease in CPU compared to pristine glass was almost 85 %. These results are supported by photographs of Petri dishes depicted in Fig. 11.

In summary, the highest antibacterial effect against both bacterial strains was observed on the glass_pl_Cu_400s_RT sample. With increasing sputtering time, the thickness of the Cu film increases, leading to a more consistent coating with a higher amount of Cu that could kill the bacteria. However, the annealing process makes the Cu film oxidized, and CuO has lower or even no antibacterial activity compared to bulk copper. This is consistent with the measurements of zeta potential (Fig. 9), where all the samples except glass_pl_Cu_400s_RT showed negative surface charge. The positive surface charge of this sample was explained by washing off and dissolving the Cu cations with antibacterial activity into the electrolyte solution.

The prepared Cu layers were tested also from the point of their possible cytotoxicity for mammalian cells. For that reason, firstly 24 h eluates from as-deposited and dewetted Cu layers were prepared in a standard cell culture medium, which was used for cultivation of fibroblasts (NHDF) and liver cells (HepG2) for 24 h. Before any analysis, images of the cells cultivated in different eluates were taken by a microscope (Fig. 12). The images indicate that the cell number of fibroblasts cultivated in the eluates from Cu layers is decreased (irrespective of Cu layer treatment), which is proved by an analysis of cell number by fluorescent DNA staining in Fig. 13A. Differences in the number of hepatoma cells is from the images in Fig. 12 not obvious, which is also demonstrated by fluorescent cell number measurement (Fig. 13B). It can suggest that the different cell types are differently sensitive to the same eluates, which is demonstrated by reduced cell numbers in case of fibroblasts.

Surprisingly, a big difference was determined in a metabolic activity of single cell between fibroblasts and liver cells. The eluates from Cu layers induced a significant increase of metabolic activity of fibroblasts in comparison to fibroblasts cultivated in a standard medium, however, the Cu layers induced a significant decrease in the activity of liver cells. In summary, the fibroblasts decreased their cell number but remaining cells increased their metabolic activity, whereas liver cells significantly reduced their metabolic activity (under cytotoxic level) while maintaining cell numbers (still attached to the surface but visibly weak). Thus, the eluates from Cu layers have already some effect on the cells suggesting some sample instability.

Secondly, the fibroblasts and liver cells were directly seeded on Cu layers and pristine glass sample. Thus, the influence of the surface properties as well as eluates can be determined. Cell images before any analyses were taken in bright field by microscope firstly (Fig. 14), and then their metabolic activity was determined (Fig. 15). The fibroblasts cultivated on both Cu layers (glass_pl_Cu_400s_RT and glass_pl_Cu_400s_300 °C) were mostly round not attached to the layers

anymore after 24 h of incubation. This was also confirmed by detection of their decreased metabolic activity. Despite the fibroblast activity is significantly decreased on both Cu layers, significant difference is apparent also between the two layers. Cells are presented in higher number and with higher activity on the dewetted sample than on as-deposited one. Similar reaction is apparent in the liver cells (Fig. 15), however, the decrease in their activity on both Cu layers is even stronger than in the fibroblasts. This suggests that the liver cells are more sensitive to these newly prepared materials than fibroblasts.

The cells cultivated on Cu layers were also stained by Live/Dead assay to prove their response on the material also by other technique. Obtained fluorescent images of living (green) cells and dead (red) cells (Fig. 16) confirm previous results. Both cell types on the as-deposited Cu layer react more negatively to it than to the dewetted Cu layer. This could be explained by different surface properties of the prepared Cu layers. More stabilized and nano-rough dewetted Cu layer provided better surface properties for cell adhesion (irrespective of cell type) than as deposited Cu layer. Similar behaviour was observed on gold nanostructured glass substrate [53].

4. Conclusions

In conclusion, the study focused on enhancing the adhesion of nanosized Cu films to a glass substrate, a crucial aspect for their applications in electronics and medicine. The combination of Ar plasma etching, magnetron sputtering, and solid-state dewetting demonstrated significant improvements and changes in surface properties such as Cu concentration, UV-Vis absorption, conductivity, and surface roughness. XPS analysis provided a nuanced understanding of surface chemistry and the material continuity of Cu layers. A transition from material discontinuity to continuity was detected with increasing sputtering time. The oxidation process, with the initial formation of Cu₂O followed by CuO formation during dewetting, was revealed through careful analysis. AFM analyses revealed heightened surface roughness due to annealing, displaying a rugged morphology characterized by isolated island-like nanostructures of CuO. This surface transformation caused an increase in contact angle values, yet the surface remained hydrophilic. The loss of surface plasmon resonance in UV-Vis spectra also occurred due to the transformation of copper from a metal to an oxide during dewetting. Electrical conductivity, a critical aspect in electronic applications, exhibited a remarkable transformation, with electrically continuous layers formed after 100 s of Cu sputtering, resulting in a 13-order magnitude decrease in sheet resistance to 35 Ω. In contrast, dewetted samples exhibited a gradual decrease in sheet resistance attributed to the presence of semiconducting CuO. Notably, despite the dewetting process reduced the adhesion of layers, the Ar plasma etching significantly improved adhesion of both Cu layers (as-deposited and dewetted) to glass substrate. Biological testing demonstrated the as-deposited Cu layer's pronounced bactericidal and cytotoxic effect compared to the dewetted samples. These findings underscore the delicate balance between structural changes induced by dewetting and the desired enhancement in adhesion and biological performance. Reduced number of colony producing units confirms that our copper nanostructured samples could find applications as antibacterial coatings for biomedical devices. Further, optimized process offers a promising avenue for the development of copper-based materials with improved reliability in electronic and medical applications, however, the expected properties are still not ideal, which lays the foundation for further advancements in nanomaterial design.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Alena Reznickova: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Veronika Lacmanova:** Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Marie Hubalek Kalbacova:** Writing – original draft,

Formal analysis. **Petr Hausild:** Formal analysis. **Jiri Nohava:** Formal analysis. **Zdenka Kolska:** Resources, Formal analysis. **Anna Kutova:** Formal analysis. **Petr Slepicka:** Formal analysis.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13756480>.

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